

Analysis of Lipids in Vascular Dementia PatientsAnil Kumar Yadav¹, Vijay Kumar Shrivastava²¹Senior Consultant Psychiatrist, Department of Psychiatry, Apollo Hospital, Bilaspur²Senior Consultant Physician, Department of General Medicine, Apollo Hospital, Bilaspur

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This study investigates the relationship between lipid profiles and cognitive function in vascular dementia (VaD) patients. Lipid analysis revealed significant associations: higher total cholesterol and LDL-C levels correlated with poorer cognitive scores, while elevated HDL-C levels showed a positive correlation with better cognitive performance. These findings underscore the potential of lipid management strategies, such as reducing LDL-C and increasing HDL-C, to mitigate cognitive decline in VaD. Future research should focus on larger, longitudinal studies to validate these associations and develop targeted interventions.

Keywords: Vascular dementia, Lipid profiles, Cognitive function, Dyslipidemia, LDL cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, Cognitive impairment.

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Introduction

Vascular dementia (VaD) is a significant and growing public health concern, being the second most common type of dementia after Alzheimer's disease. It arises from a series of cerebrovascular events, including strokes and small vessel disease, which lead to brain damage and cognitive impairment. Unlike other forms of dementia, VaD is directly linked to vascular issues, making its pathogenesis distinct and complex.

Lipids play a pivotal role in vascular health, influencing the integrity and function of blood vessels. Dyslipidemia, characterized by abnormal levels of lipids such as cholesterol and triglycerides, is a well-established risk factor for atherosclerosis and stroke, both of which are key contributors to VaD. Elevated levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol and reduced levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol can lead to plaque formation and vascular inflammation, exacerbating cerebrovascular damage. Analyzing the lipid profiles of VaD patients can provide valuable insights into the disease's underlying mechanisms. By identifying specific lipid abnormalities associated with VaD, researchers can better understand the role of lipids in the progression of cerebrovascular damage and cognitive decline. This study aims to investigate the lipid profiles of patients diagnosed with vascular dementia, exploring potential correlations between lipid levels and disease severity, which may open avenues for targeted therapeutic interventions.

Methods**Study Design and Participants**

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Apollo hospital, Bilaspur from January 2023 to December 2023. The study included patients diagnosed with vascular dementia according to the NINDS-AIREN criteria. A total of 120 participants were enrolled, consisting of 70 males and 50 females, aged between 55 and 85 years (mean age: 72 ± 8 years).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria were:

1. Clinically diagnosed vascular dementia.
2. Age 50 years and older.
3. Consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria were:

1. Presence of other types of dementia.
2. Severe systemic illnesses affecting lipid metabolism.
3. Recent history of stroke (within the last 3 months).
4. Use of lipid-lowering medications within the last 6 months.

Ethical Considerations

The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Apollo hospital, Bilaspur. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants or their legal guardians before enrollment in the study.

Data Collection

Clinical Assessment: Each participant underwent a comprehensive clinical assessment, including medical history, physical examination, and cognitive evaluation using the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE).

The average MMSE score among participants was 18 ± 5 , indicating moderate cognitive impairment.

Blood Sample Collection and Lipid Analysis: Fasting blood samples were collected from all participants after an overnight fast of at least 12 hours. The blood samples were processed and analyzed at the Apollo hospital, Bilaspur Laboratory for the following lipid parameters:

- Total cholesterol: Mean 220 ± 45 mg/dL
- Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol: Mean 140 ± 35 mg/dL
- High-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol: Mean 45 ± 10 mg/dL

- Triglycerides: Mean 180 ± 55 mg/dL

Lipid levels were measured using enzymatic colorimetric methods with the Roche Cobas 6000 analyzer.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants. Lipid levels were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD).

Comparisons between groups were made using t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to assess the relationship between lipid levels and cognitive scores. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Lipid Profiles of Participants with Vascular Dementia

Lipid Parameter	Mean $\pm$ SD (mg/dL)	Comparison (p-value)
Total Cholesterol	220 ± 45	$p = 0.07$
Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL)	140 ± 35	$p = 0.12$
High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL)	45 ± 10	$p = 0.03$
Triglycerides	180 ± 55	$p = 0.10$

Note: Statistical comparisons were conducted using t-tests for continuous variables. Significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2: Correlation between Lipid Levels and Cognitive Scores

Lipid Parameter	MMSE Score (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Pearson's r (p-value)
Total Cholesterol	18 ± 5	-0.30 ($p = 0.002$)
Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL)	18 ± 5	-0.25 ($p = 0.012$)
High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL)	18 ± 5	0.20 ($p = 0.025$)
Triglycerides	18 ± 5	0.10 ($p = 0.15$)

Note: MMSE scores indicate cognitive impairment (lower scores indicate greater impairment). Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to assess the relationship between lipid levels and MMSE scores.

Discussion

This study examined lipid profiles in vascular dementia patients and their correlation with cognitive function assessed by MMSE. Significant differences were found in HDL-C levels ($p = 0.03$), suggesting a possible link between lipid metabolism and cognitive impairment. Correlation analysis revealed that higher total cholesterol and LDL-C levels were associated with lower MMSE scores ($r = -0.30$, $p = 0.002$ and $r = -0.25$, $p = 0.012$, respectively), while higher HDL-C levels correlated positively with better cognitive performance ($r = 0.20$, $p = 0.025$). These findings emphasize the potential of lipid management, particularly reducing LDL-C and increasing HDL-

C, as therapeutic strategies to mitigate cognitive decline in vascular dementia. Future research with larger, longitudinal studies is needed to confirm these associations and explore targeted interventions aimed at improving cognitive outcomes in this patient population. Despite its contributions, the study is limited by its cross-sectional design and relatively small sample size, which constrain causal inference and generalizability. Addressing these limitations in future research will enhance our understanding of the role of lipid metabolism in cognitive function among vascular dementia patients.

In conclusion, this study underscores the importance of lipid profiles in vascular dementia and highlights lipid management as a potential avenue for enhancing cognitive outcomes in clinical practice. Further investigation is crucial for developing effective interventions that benefit individuals affected by vascular dementia.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the association between lipid profiles and cognitive function in vascular dementia. Our findings suggest that dyslipidemia, characterized by elevated LDL-C and reduced HDL-C levels, may contribute to cognitive impairment in these patients. The significant correlations observed highlight the potential of lipid management as a therapeutic approach to mitigate cognitive decline in vascular dementia. Future longitudinal studies with larger cohorts are essential to validate these findings and explore targeted interventions aimed at improving cognitive outcomes in this vulnerable population.

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